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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ACHU SHIBU bearing USN 6SU21DF001 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYAN M P bearing USN 6SU21DF002 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAND SHANKAR bearing USN 6SU21DF003 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSHREE T G bearing USN 6SU21DF004 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARYAN JAYANTH bearing USN 6SU21DF005 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ATHUL PRAKASH D bearing USN 6SU21DF006 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVADEVAN B bearing USN 6SU21DF007 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOKUL K V bearing USN 6SU21DF008 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOPIKA V V bearing USN 6SU21DF009 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GURUNATHAPPAGOUDA KARALAKUNTI bearing USN 6SU21DF010 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JIBRAN T JALEEL bearing USN 6SU21DF011 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JUAN K VARGHESE bearing USN 6SU21DF012 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANAV SUNIL bearing USN 6SU21DF013 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDHANA P bearing USN 6SU21DF014 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHIL MAHADEV bearing USN 6SU21DF015 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIVED AV bearing USN 6SU21DF016 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms P RASHAD bearing USN 6SU21DF017 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROSE THOMAS bearing USN 6SU21DF018 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANIYA A J bearing USN 6SU21DF019 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHERIN SUSAN KURIAN bearing USN 6SU21DF020 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHREYA bearing USN 6SU21DF021 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms UTHARA A M bearing USN 6SU21DF022 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FOSEAYA ANJU BEJOY bearing USN 6SU21DF023 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MIDHUN SUNILKUMAR bearing USN 6SU21DF024 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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